

Rub-Impact of Coupled Vibration of Vertical Rotor-Stator System Submerged in an Inviscid Fluid

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Abstract

The interactions between rotor-stator submerged in incompressible fluid flows are strong nonlinear phenomena that have wide applications in scientific and engineering disciplines. This paper presents vibration analysis of a vertical oscillating rotor-rub system interacted in incompressible flow regimes. The governing equation of the coupled lateral and torsional vibrations of a rotor-rub system and the inviscid fluid forces action are firstly established based on Energy Principle and Euler method for the incompressible fluid. The unsteady 5-Degree-of-Freedom system of rotor-stator-fluid motion is simulated by means of an appropriate solver. In the analysis it was found through the severity of the fault detected that the presence of inviscid fluid gives strong softening and fluctuating interferences components in the response when the rotating system is involved in rotor-stator contact. Further, the responses displayed a generally softening nonlinearity on torsional deflection of the rotor. The results reveal that, the inviscid fluid had a significant attenuation on the orbit of the shaft in comparison to a standard orbit of the rotor. The obtained results indicate that the fluid-rotor interaction considerably reduce the dynamic vibration response of the faulted rotor system.

Keywords: Fluid forces, axial force, Fluid-Structure-Interaction, rotor-stator rub, vibration analysis;

1. Introduction

The most common source of vibration in rotordynamics are related to the inertia of moving parts in the machine. Rotor-stator rub occurs regularly in real industrial machinery. However, a fatal phenomenon occurs when the rotor traverses to the full extent of the inner surface of the stator with a backward processional orbit to that of the direction of the angular speed rotation [1]. Newkirk [1] noticed the thermal character of the rub and gave a correlation with the critical speeds [2]. In the meantime, tests were performed by Taylor who used a bowed shaft to verify the theory of Newkirk that rubbing instability occurs below the critical speed while above the critical speed there is a self-balancing effect because of the inversion of the phase angle between the exciting force and dynamic deformation [3-4]. Choi and Noah [5] used Fast Fourier transform (FFT) technique to investigated rub fault by treating as linear vibration problem. They proposed an algorithm to calculate the steady state solution, and the results showed that subharmonics and super-harmonics might be found during rub impact. The rotating parts in the rotor-stator system may be surrounded by a liquid domain resulting to fluid-structure-interaction problem, one or more solid structures interact with an internal or surrounding fluid, yet a comprehensive study of such problems remains a challenge due to their high non-linearity and multidisciplinary nature [6-8]. These challenges can be categorised into three areas namely, problem formulation, numerical discretisation and fluid-structure coupling. The problem formulation takes place at the continuous level, before the discretisation. However, the modelling choices made at the continuous level have implications for the numerical discretisations that are most suitable for the case at hand [9]. Kito [10] studied the effect of fluid forces on an eccentrically rotating circular rod in a liquid medium. In his analysis, he assumed the flow velocity distribution to be linear over a gap between the rod and cylinder. Lida [11] examined the same problem, but using an infinitely extending water region, while Fritz [12] considered a circular rod rotating in a cylinder with a small gap between the rotor and cylinder; his analysis includes the influence of turbulence and Taylor vortex flow. Brennen [13] dissected

hypothetically the fluid forces following up on a circular rod rotating in a circular cylinder for laminar and turbulent flow (high and low Reynolds numbers) and Walston *et al* [14] established the dynamic behaviour of an overhanging shaft submerged in a viscous liquid. The influence of the liquid upon the critical speed and amplitude of the rotor was done experimentally. The study established a relationship condition for amplitude as a function of viscosity, velocity and mass developed with the help of statistical regression analysis. The analytical results on the fundamental critical speed of a shaft in a viscous fluid were studied by Shimogo *et al* [15]. Kadyrov *et al* [16] studied the oscillations of a rigid cylinder in a cylindrical duct filled with a viscous incompressible fluid. They used mathematical analysis and presented the theoretical results for frequency subjected to different fluid parameters. Kydyrbekuly *et al* [17] investigated generalized dynamic model of a rotor-fluid foundation system by taking into account the nonlinear stiffness of rolling bearings along with fluid and foundation vibrations. The obtained results enabled the optimization of the system parameters such as the rotor, foundation, fluid, reducing stresses along the contact surfaces, forced vibrations amplitudes as well as the width of instability zones.

Rotor-stator system operating in high speed induced strong vibrations which may create high fluctuation and complex feature extractions when the system generated a hydrodynamic resistance forces. The present work is devoted towards established a mathematical model for the coupled lateral and torsional vibrations with presence of axial force in vertical oscillating rotor. The rotor-stator rub impact model is used to accommodate the impact and derived the normal and friction forces. The result of governing equations of the hydrodynamic forces are fully coupled with varying coefficients of the vertical rotor system under the effect of axial excitation. The response to a coupled rotor-stator rub submerged by inviscid fluid are finally obtained through numerical simulation.

2. Mathematical model of vertical rotor-stator contact

Figure 1 (a) represents a schematic diagram of vertical disc-shaft submerged in incompressible fluid with parametrically excited system with an external fluid force, flexible coupled which connected between centerline of the bearing and an electrical motor executing a lateral whirling motion at its Z-axis. The coupled lateral-torsional vibrations of a vertical unbalanced rotor-rub system model are established based on mechanical energy law, system differential equation of motion are obtained by introducing classical Lagrangian approach. The system involves axial force, normal and tangential force at the contact point between rotor and stator. The model integrates the following assumptions: (1) A simple Jeffcott approach with no gravity force which considers the system as a massive rigid disc mounted midway between the flexible couple and bearing on a massless flexible shaft, (2) the moving mass, M is not only the mass of the disc but the modal mass that corresponds to the first lateral mode of the system, (3) the shaft rotates only below the second-lateral critical speed, (4) the lateral and shaft flexural stiffness are the same and its relatively small compared to the bearing stiffness, (5) the bearing is assumed to be self-aligning with linear viscous damping effects only, and (6) the gyroscopic effects due to disc spinning are neglected.

Figure 1: (a) Motor-shaft-disc-stator-stator and axial force, (b) Section view of disc on the shaft in inertial, rotating and motor coordinates

2.1 Kinetic energy expression

The system degree of freedom are lumped on the disc as two orthogonal lateral deflections of the disc's geometrical centre (X, Y, Z), one longitudinal deflection Z in the presence of an axial force P , one rigid-body rotation, θ and one torsional deflection angle, ψ . The coordinate systems used are shown in Figure 1(b), where XYZ is the inertial reference frame, $x_m y_m z_m$ represents the body motor shaft coordinate system which is rotating with the torsional undeflected system, xyz is a body coordinate system of the disc which is attached to the disc and exhibits all its motions. The unbalance mass, m_u , location is described by the eccentricity vector e with respect to the disc body co-ordinate system xyz .

$$T_D = \frac{1}{2}M(\dot{X}^2 + \dot{Y}^2 + \dot{Z}^2) + \frac{1}{2}J_D(\dot{\theta} + \dot{\psi})^2 + \frac{1}{2}J_M\dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_u\dot{R}_e^T\dot{R}_e \quad (1)$$

2.2 Potential energy expression

The system potential energy consists of the shaft bending strain energy and the torsional strain energy. The elastic strain energy of the shaft is given by:

$$U = \frac{1}{2}K_{XX}X^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{YY}Y^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{ZZ}Z^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{\psi\psi}\psi^2 \quad (2)$$

where the modal stiffness is $K_{XX} = K_{YY} = K_{ZZ} = K_0 - P\pi^2/2L$ and the system torsional stiffness $K_{\psi\psi} = K_T - m_u e^2 \dot{\theta}^2$. It is assumed that the shaft is subjected to an axial force P as follows [18]:

$$P = P_o + P_f \sin\theta \quad (3)$$

Taken into account the effect of damping coefficient, the Rayleigh's dissipation function can be expressed as:

$$R = \frac{1}{2}C_{XX}\dot{X}^2 + \frac{1}{2}C_{YY}\dot{Y}^2 + \frac{1}{2}C_{ZZ}\dot{Z}^2 + \frac{1}{2}C_{\psi\psi}\dot{\psi}^2 \quad (4)$$

2.3 Equation of motion

Upon substituting the kinetic, potential energy and Rayleigh's dissipation function expressions into the Lagrange's equations and performing the needed differentiation and algebraic manipulations, the application of the Lagrange equations provides a matrix equation of the form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} m_{\theta\theta} & m_{\theta\psi} & m_{\theta X} & m_{\theta Y} & m_{\theta Z} \\ m_{\psi\theta} & m_{\psi\psi} & m_{\psi X} & m_{\psi Y} & 0 \\ m_{X\theta} & m_{X\psi} & m_{XX} & 0 & m_{XZ} \\ m_{Y\theta} & m_{Y\psi} & 0 & m_{YY} & m_{YZ} \\ m_{Z\theta} & 0 & m_{ZX} & m_{ZY} & m_{ZZ} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{\theta} \\ \ddot{\psi} \\ \ddot{X} \\ \ddot{Y} \\ \ddot{Z} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_{\psi\psi} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{XX} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{YY} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{ZZ} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{\psi} \\ \dot{X} \\ \dot{Y} \\ \dot{Z} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_{\psi\psi} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{XX} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{YY} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & K_{ZZ} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \theta \\ \psi \\ X \\ Y \\ Z \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Q_\theta \\ 0 \\ Q_X \\ Q_Y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F_\theta \\ F_\psi \\ F_X \\ F_Y \\ F_Z \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Where the first element matrix represents the mass matrix, which shows coupling between the system degree of freedom. $\{Q_n\}$ represents the non-linear array which the components shows to be function of the system rotational speed, the torsional deformation angle and its time derivative and the mass imbalance. The non-linear terms corresponding to the system lateral d.o.f.s, X and Y explicated in [19]. $\{F_n\}$ represents the external excitation force associated with each degree of freedom.

2.4 Rub force expression

The equations of the rub impact force have been already derived using the model presented in figure 2. The mathematical phenomenon being the nonlinearity due to the rub effect is happened when a rotor makes contact with

a stator $R > \delta$, where $R = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2}$ is the radial displacement of the rotor, δ the clearance between rotor and stator.

The radial impact force F_N and the tangential rub force F_T can be written as:

$$\begin{cases} F_N = (e - \delta)k_r \\ F_T = \mu F_N \end{cases} \quad (r \geq \delta) \quad (6)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient between the stator and rotor, k_r is the radial stiffness of the stator. In the O - XY coordinate system, these two forces can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} F_{X_rub} \\ F_{Y_rub} \end{bmatrix} = -H(e - \delta) \frac{(e - \delta)k_r}{e} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\mu \\ \mu & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where H is the Heaviside function, which can be defined as

$$H(X) = \begin{cases} 0 & X < 0 \\ 1 & X \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Figure 2. Geometry of rotor, rubbing impact forces and a clearance

3. Mathematical model of rotating inviscid fluid

In this section, the hydrodynamic pressure and the liquid hydrodynamic forces acting on the shaft structure are estimated under translational excitations. It is assumed that under shaft excitation, the inviscid fluid does not participate in the rotor system motion. As the inviscid fluid is considered, the linearized fluid field equations are applied to estimate the mass of the fluid participating in the rotor motion. Due to the eccentric mass, it is assumed that the vibration force from the rotor at the start up is considered as sinusoidal and orientated laterally with respect to the vertical container. The hydrodynamic resistance loads acting on the rotor is therefore determined under forced excitation and it's derived by integrating the pressure distribution over the container area.

3.1 Hydrodynamic force under lateral excitation force

Considering the upright rectangular container partially filled with an irrotational, inviscid, and incompressible fluid, and subjected to sinusoidal excitation along the x-axis,

$$X(t) = X_0 \sin \Omega t \quad (9)$$

where X_0 and Ω are the excitation amplitude and frequency, respectively, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Rectangular tank under sinusoidal lateral excitation

For a two dimensional fluid motion and under the assumption that the amplitudes of excitation and fluid response are small, the disc and the shaft are slightly having the same radius. The normal mode frequencies are determined from the linearized free-surface boundary condition and the linearized fluid field equations take the form [20]:

$$\tilde{\Phi} = -X_0 \Omega \cos \theta \cos \Omega t \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2R}{(\xi_{1n}^2 - 1)} \frac{\Omega^2}{(\omega_{1n}^2 - \Omega^2)} \frac{J_1(\xi_{1n} r / R)}{J_1(\xi_{1n})} \frac{\cosh(\xi_{1n}(z+h)/R)}{\cosh(\xi_{1n} h / R)} \right] \quad (10)$$

The hydrodynamic pressure at any point due to liquid motion (by neglecting the hydrostatic pressure, $(\rho g z)$) may be determined from the pressure equation

$$p = \rho \frac{\partial \tilde{\Phi}}{\partial t} = \rho X_0 \Omega^2 \cos \theta \cos \Omega t \left\{ r + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2R}{(\xi_{1n}^2 - 1)} \frac{\Omega^2}{(\omega_{1n}^2 - \Omega^2)} \frac{J_1(\xi_{1n} r / R)}{J_1(\xi_{1n})} \frac{\cosh(\xi_{1n}(z+h)/R)}{\cosh(\xi_{1n} h / R)} \right] \right\} \quad (11)$$

The maximum pressure occurs on the wall at $r = R$, $\theta = 0$, and $\Omega t = \pi/2$. It is given by the expression

$$\frac{p_w}{\rho g R (X_0 / R)} = \frac{\Omega^2 R}{g} \left\{ 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2}{(\xi_{1n}^2 - 1)} \frac{\Omega^2 R / \xi_{1n} g \tanh(\xi_{1n} h / R)}{(1 - \Omega^2 R / \xi_{1n} g \tanh(\xi_{1n} h / R))} \frac{\cosh(\xi_{1n}(z+h)/R)}{\cosh(\xi_{1n} h / R)} \right] \right\} \quad (12)$$

Where r is elementary width of the container; Similarly, the pressure distribution on the bottom at $z = -h$, $\theta = 0$, and $\Omega t = \pi/2$, is

$$\frac{p_b}{\rho g R (X_0 / R)} = \frac{\Omega^2 R}{g} \left\{ \frac{r}{R} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{2}{(\xi_{1n}^2 - 1)} \frac{\Omega^2 R / \xi_{1n} g \tanh(\xi_{1n} h / R)}{(1 - \Omega^2 R / \xi_{1n} g \tanh(\xi_{1n} h / R))} \frac{J_1(\xi_{1n} r / R)}{J_1(\xi_{1n})} \right] \right\} \quad (13)$$

The integer n is the circumferential mode representing the rotor deformation. Considering the oscillation in the $n = 1$ first mode such that the net hydrodynamic force components acting on the tank wall and bottom are obtained by integrating the pressure over the corresponding area of the boundary. Resolving along $\theta = 0$, one can obtain the force acting along the X-axis as [20].

$$F_x = \int_{\theta=0}^{2\pi} \int_{z=-h}^0 p \cos \theta R d\theta dz \Rightarrow F_x = m_f X_0 \Omega^2 \sin \Omega t \times \left\{ 1 + \frac{2R}{(\xi_{1n}^2 - 1)} \frac{\Omega^2}{(\omega_{1n}^2 - \Omega^2)} \frac{\tanh(\xi_{1n} h / R)}{\xi_{1n} h} \right\} \quad (14)$$

where $m_f = \rho \pi h R^2$ is the total mass of the fluid. The force acting along the y-axis and on the bottom are

$$F_y = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-h}^0 p \sin \theta R d\theta dz = 0 \quad F_b = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^R p r d\theta dr = 0 \quad (15)$$

These results indicate that there is a net force exerted along the direction of excitation as given by relation (14). In the perpendicular direction, the pressure distribution is symmetrical about the tank wall such that the integration over it vanishes. The pressure at the tank bottom produces no forces in the direction of axial excitation force. Therefore, the hydrodynamic force can be rewrite as

$$F_x = -M_{fl} \frac{d^2 Y}{dt^2} \quad \text{where } M_{fl} = m_f X_0 \left\{ \frac{1}{R} + \frac{2}{(\xi^2 - 1)} \frac{\Omega^2}{(\omega^2 - \Omega^2)} \frac{\tanh(\xi h / R)}{\xi h} \right\} \quad (16)$$

For irrotational, inviscid, and incompressible flow the added mass of fluid is coupled to the inertial force of the shaft as

$$m_{xx} = m_{yy} = M + m_u + M_{fl} \quad (17)$$

3.2 Damping in rectangular containers

Basically, the damping factor will depends on the liquid height, and container width for rectangular cross-section. When the above expression $\omega_{1n}^2 = g \xi_{1mn} / R \tanh(\xi_{1mn} h / R)$ of the liquid free-surface approaches a constant value for $h / R > 2$, $\tanh(\xi_{1mn} h / R) \approx 1$ and for the first asymmetric mode in a circular rotor $\xi_1 = 1.841$ and $\omega_{1n}^2 = g \xi_{1mn} / R$ [20] where R is the width of the container, g is the gravitational acceleration.

4. Model properties

The mechanical and geometrical properties used in the simulations are presented in Table 1.

Table1. Rotor model properties [18]

Shaft property						
J_D	0.1861 kg.m ²	K_{xx}, K_{zz}	5x10 ⁵ N/m	m_u	10 ⁻⁴ kg	ζ_t 0.3
J_M	0.36 kg.m ²	C_{xx}, C_{zz}	100, 44 kg/s	K_s	5x10 ⁷ N/m	Rd 0.15 m
M	16.47 kg	C_T	0.08 kg/s	e	0.015	ζ_l 0.0175
Fluid property						
T	20°C	ω_n	6.0084 rd/s	ρ	1004 kg/m ³	Ω 4.8522 rad/s

A simple rectangular container with uniform cross-section area, length 1 m, width 0.5 m, with excitation amplitude ratios, $X_0/R = 0.1666$ is considered for numerical analysis. Figure 4 shows the balanced shaft with various coupling forces. Based on Eq. (6) and Eq. (16), dynamic responses of the rotor system can be obtained using Runge-Kutta method by the aid of Matlab. A numerical simulation was conducted under the baseline condition and fault conditions presented as follows. 1. Unbalance is the only fault in the rotor system. 2. Rotor-stator rub condition: a rub forces are assumed normal and tangential to the peripheral disc on the shaft and is accompanied by unbalance as well. 3. Submerged condition: in addition to unbalance and rubs the rotor system is immersed in Inviscid fluid and simulated as outlined in Section 5. Using the lateral direction, the orbit of shaft centre and the frequency spectrum of the signal.

5. Numerical simulation results and discussion

5.1 Unbalanced rotor system response

Firstly, a numerical simulation of the unbalanced system with the effect of the vertical axial force was conducted under the condition without inviscid fluid effects while the rotor is passing its first critical speed. The unbalance vibration responses, the orbit patterns of shaft centre and the frequency spectrum of the response in lateral direction are presented in Figure 5. And then, another numerical simulation considering immersion of the rotor system into inviscid fluid domain was carried out at the same first critical speed as displayed in Figure 6. In addition the presence of rotor rub contact was also analysed and compared in the air and inviscid fluid domain, the response are displayed in Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively.

Figure 5: Response of unbalanced rotor system while the rotor is passing its first critical speed.

Figure 6: Response of unbalanced rotor system immersed in inviscid fluid at rotor first critical speed.

Comparing Figure 5 with Figure 6, it's obvious that when fluid effects occur in a submerged rotor system, vibration responses displayed by orbits patterns is distorted and cease to be pure harmonic signals as shown in Figure 5 (c) and Figure. 6 (c). In immersed fluid the shaft centre orbit in x and y direction distort and is not a standard circle anymore as shown in Figure 6 (c). Simultaneously, From Figure 5 (d) and Figure 6(d), it can be noted that, apart from the basic harmonic (57.8Hz), there are also small peaks of sub-harmonics in the frequency spectrum. In addition, the lateral deflection of vibration of a rotor while passing through the first critical speed can be observed in both Figure 5 (a) and Figure. 6 (a), where the vibration increases with respect to time until reaching the maximum amplitude response level of 3.1×10^{-3} m and 4.81×10^{-3} m in inviscid fluid then decreases progressively afterwards. The lateral responses for this two

cases showed a similar pattern and also did not exhibit any changes for unbalanced rotor in inviscid conditions. The spectrum of the torsional vibration increases dramatically as illustrated in Figure 6 (d), however, the torsional vibration are influenced by the hydrodynamic forces which decreases gradually the torsional deflection according to the critical speeds Figure 6 (d). The fluid effect slowly enabled stabilizing the torsional deflection of the rotor system. More precisely, it can be seen in Figure 5 (b) that the torsional deflections amplitudes increase abruptly with no apparent frequency in the rotating plan. It appears in Figure 6 (b) that the system is perfectly stable and takes a static position in the rotating frame in inviscid medium.

5.2 Response of unbalanced rotor system with rub effect

In the case of an unbalanced rotor with rub, the fluid effects influences significantly the rub impact. An interesting behavior observed in Figure 8 is about the effect of the hydrodynamic force on the system stability. As it is seen, existence of a rub on the unbalanced rotor causes the instability in a highly disturbed rotor system and this effect is intensified proportionally with the axial excitation forces for a given rub clearance ($\delta = 6 \times 10^{-4} \text{m}$ selected).

Figure 7. Response of unbalanced rotor-stator system with rub

Figure 8. Response of unbalanced rotor-stator system with rub immersed in inviscid fluid

This behavior shows that the rub on the vertical rotor with axial excitation forces would practically reinforce the high vibration of the system and causing its destruction. As it is obvious from the Figure 7 (a) and Figure 8(a), when the hydrodynamic forces is applied the vibration response decreases smoothly. The results indicate that any interaction of the fluid with the rotor is followed by reduction of the natural frequencies Figure 8 (d) and augmentation of stability Figure 8 (c) comparing to Figure 7 (c). This means that increasing the hydrodynamic forces makes the torsional motion of rotor to be stiffer Figure 7 (b) and Figure 8 (b).

6. Conclusion

This paper developed a numerical simulation of the unsteady 5-DOF system corresponding to a rotational, a torsional deformation, two lateral deflections and one axial excitation of rotor-stator system submerged in incompressible inviscid fluid. The coupled torsional and lateral vibrations of a vertical unbalanced rotor-stator rub was developed using the Lagrangian formulation, and fluid equation was modelled using Euler method. The study brings out the nature of the spectral components of nonlinear, harmonic and sub-harmonic response for unbalance and rotor-stator rubbing faults by means of waveform signal, orbits and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) techniques. The nonlinear dynamic response of vertical excited rotor-stator interacting with inviscid fluid revealed irregular rotor motions due to recurrent rub impact generated and internal resonance with some harmonic peaks of excitation. The rub excitation features consisted of a sup-harmonic peak which reflects the presence of rub, with a frequency near to twice the fundamental resonance frequency. It was found that the presence of inviscid fluid gives more strongly softening results when the rotating system is involved to rotor-stator contact. It was also found that the responses displayed a generally softening nonlinearity on torsional deflection of the operating rotor and the inviscid fluid have a larger attenuation of the orbit shaft to a standard circle. Therefore, obtained results indicated that the fluid-rotor interaction reduces the dynamic vibration response of the faulted system running below the second critical speed.

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